

Capital Structure Impact on Operating Profit in Vietnamese Listed Companies: The Moderating Role of the Board of Directors

Diem, Ngo Nhat Phuong^a

^aFaculty of Accounting and Auditing, University of Finance - Marketing, Hochiminh City, Vietnam. Email: ngodiem@ufm.edu.vn.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0145-8000>.

Abstract

Background: Capital structure (CT) is a controversial issue. Although numerous studies on CT have been conducted, their results are not uniform.

Objective: This study examines the operating profit of listed companies in Vietnam's emerging market, aiming to evaluate the impact of capital structure (CT) on the operating profit of listed companies in Vietnam's emerging market. At the same time, it examined the board of directors as a moderating variable of the impact of capital structure on operating profitability.

Methodology: The dataset used in this study was the financial reports and annual reports of listed companies on the Vietnamese stock market in the period 2015 to 2023. FGLS regression was employed, with dependent variables representing Return on Assets and Return on Equity, which are measures of profit.

Result: The regression results reveal that CT is negatively correlated to ROA and ROE. However, board size moderates the negative impact of CT on ROA and ROE, and duality increases the positive impact of CT on ROA and ROE.

Conclusion: In the emerging Vietnamese economy, CT reduces operating profitability, and board characteristics can moderate the negative impact of CT on profitability.

Unique contributions: This study has made significant contributions to the discovery of the negative impact of CT on the profitability of listed companies in Vietnam. The study also provides evidence that acknowledges the effectiveness of board monitoring on debt use in the emerging market of Vietnam.

Key recommendation: Future studies should expand their consideration of short-term and long-term debt types that affect profits, as well as the moderating role of internal and external governance mechanisms, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of this issue.

Keywords: Capital structure, profit, board of directors, Vietnam.

Introduction

Profit is a matter of concern for businesses, but it is affected by capital structure directly or indirectly, and an ideal capital structure increases operating efficiency and profits (Nguyen et al., 2023). Therefore, the decision on CT is the most important decision made by executives because it is related to growth as well as increased profits (Ayaz et al., 2021). Capital structure is the allocation of equity and debt to serve business operations, giving rise to the cost of capital and is the basis for determining profits, so capital structure and its impact on profits are issues of interest in finance and are explained by several theories. Specifically, the Modigliani–Miller theory (MM theory) (Modigliani & Miller, 1958) suggests that CT does not affect profit with the assumption that the enterprise operates in a perfect capital market. However, this assumption is not suitable in practice, so many researchers have provided additional explanations showing that CT affects the performance of the company, especially after the agency theory was published (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) with the recognition that optimal CT reduces conflicts of interest between parties, restricts or encourages managers to act to increase value for shareholders, thereby improving profit, maximizing the firm value. This means that capital structure affects performance, so many empirical studies have been conducted to assess the impact of CT on firm performance over the past decades, but the results of these studies are contradictory. Some studies acknowledge that CT has a positive impact on profitability (Ayuba et al., 2019; Chowdhury & Chowdhury, 2010; Khan et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2023). Contrary to the above view, some studies provide evidence that CT hurts operating efficiency, reducing profits with the view that high debt increases bankruptcy risk, thereby reducing firm value and profits (Dang et al., 2019; Dawar, 2014; Le & Phan, 2017; Bui et al., 2023). The reasons for different research results may be due to random factors and may be due to the impact of regulatory factors (Pham & Nguyen, 2019). Therefore, it is necessary to consider regulatory factors when studying the relationship between CT and operating profits.

Corporate governance (CG) is an important mechanism in the unit, so even if the company has an optimal capital structure, if the CG is not effective, the company may face a financial crisis (Kijkasiwat et al., 2022). Companies that comply with CG have better management capabilities, effective monitoring and supervision mechanisms, providing development opportunities and better access to resources, thereby improving operational efficiency, increasing profits, as well as minimising risks (Bhagat & Bolton, 2019). Previous studies have recognised that CG has different impacts on the CT of the company, and this impact is also different in developed and emerging markets (Pham & Nguyen, 2019). The agency problem will be solved when the company has a good CG mechanism, and good CG increases the monitoring role of managers, so using debt financing can increase operating efficiency (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). However, the moderating role of CG on the impact of CT on profit has not been of interest to researchers (Pham & Nguyen, 2019). Therefore, we conducted this study in the Vietnamese market to assess the moderating effect of individual factors of CG, typically the representation of the board of directors (BD), on the relationship between CT and operating profit.

The Vietnamese market is used for this study because Vietnam is an emerging market with typical characteristics of emerging markets, such as a rapid growth rate and an incomplete legal and financial system (World Bank, 2018). Moreover, the research context in the Vietnamese market has characteristics that may be different from those in other countries, such as culture, development level, political institutions, living standards, and many other aspects (Truong & Nguyen, 2024). In

addition, in emerging markets, principal-agent conflicts of interest are more common and may influence CT decisions (Dharwadkar et al., 2000).

The study has several contributions to existing theory as follows. First, we add to the existing evidence on the impact of CT on the operating profit of listed companies in Vietnam's emerging market. Although the evidence on the impact of financial leverage on performance has been widely studied, the results are not consistent. Next, this study provides additional evidence demonstrating the moderating role of BD on the relationship between CT and operating profit.

In addition to section 1, which deals with the introduction, section 2 provides a theoretical background and hypotheses. Part 3 is the methodology. Next, Part 4 presents the descriptive statistics research results and discussion, and Part 5 concludes with conclusions and managerial implications.

Theoretical background and hypotheses development

Foundational theory

The study uses a combination of theories to explain the impact of CT on operating profits of listed companies, explaining CG as a moderator of this relationship. The MM theory is considered the foundational theory (Modigliani & Miller, 1958), which argues that corporate profits are affected by CT. MM theory assumes that firms operate in a perfect market, there is no bankruptcy, information is perfect and available, so profits do not depend on capital structure. However, when the market is not perfect, meaning the above assumption does not exist, the result will be different, or CT has an impact on operating profits. The pecking order theory suggests that the use of financial resources is always hierarchical (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Internal sources of finance are preferred over external sources of finance. Interest must be paid so that the cost of debt capital is always less than the cost of equity capital. In addition, the trade-off theory (Kraus & Litzenberger, 1973), the company will trade off the cost of debt with the benefits of debt to maximise operating profits. Using debt reduces tax liability because income is reduced due to interest payments on loans, so debt is considered a tax shield (Modigliani & Miller, 1958). Agency theory suggests that there exists a conflict of interest between parties, and the optimal capital structure can minimise agency costs. Additionally, when a firm has high debt, managers are pressured to invest in profitable projects to generate enough cash flow to pay interest (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). At the same time, when the CT has a high debt ratio, creditors often demand high interest rates to compensate for the risk so that debt may have a negative impact on profits.

Overview of empirical studies and research hypotheses

CT is a strategic decision of the firm and has received much research. A company with better prospects will issue more debt and have a lower debt ratio than companies with poor prospects. Some studies acknowledge the positive impact of CT on operating profits with the view that high debt improves operating efficiency, increasing profits (Dakua, 2019; Chowdhury & Chowdhury, 2010; Khan et al., 2021). On the contrary, other views argue that debt reduces profits by incurring the costs of financial distress (Kraus & Litzenberger, 1973). Companies incur debts, so they must periodically pay interest, which limits working capital for business operations (Sarkar & Sarkar, 2008). Therefore, the lack of working capital for business operations can prevent the company

from seizing high-yield investment opportunities, and this affects profits. Therefore, some views suggest that CT has a negative impact on operating profits (Dang et al., 2019; Dawar, 2014; Nguyen et al., 2023). The inconsistent empirical results are because the studies were conducted in different countries with different political institutions, different operating markets, and different corporate governance mechanisms. For example, the study of (Le & Phan, 2017) (Dang et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2023) used a dataset of listed companies in the emerging market of Vietnam, the emerging market of India (Dakua, 2019); and used a dataset in the Nigerian market (Ayuba et al., 2019). The difference in the existing literature on research results may be due to the lack of mention of situations and contexts that can regulate the relationship between CT and profitability (Jermias, 2008). Situations and contexts that can affect this relationship may be CG factors, company size, and political institutions. Meanwhile, studies conducted in the Vietnamese market, such as (Dang et al., 2019; Bui et al., 2023; Le & Phan, 2017; Nguyen et al., 2023), assessed the impact of capital structure on performance but did not use moderating variables on this relationship. That is why this study, in addition to assessing the impact of CT on operating profit, focuses on examining the moderating role of each factor representing CG on the relationship between CT and operating profit. First, the first hypothesis is proposed:

*H₁: CT has a negative impact on operating profit in Vietnamese listed companies.
The moderating role of the board of directors*

CG is a mechanism to resolve agency problems when conflicts of interest arise between owners and agents (Kijkasiwat et al., 2022). CG is the set of relationships between managers, BD, shareholders and stakeholders, in which the BD is considered one of the key elements of CG (Dharwadkar et al., 2000). Jensen & Meckling (1976) acknowledge that the BD is an effective internal monitoring mechanism and monitors the performance of managers (Kijkasiwat et al., 2022). Because the BD is one of the internal governance mechanisms (Kumar & Singh, 2013), the BD performs the function of protecting the company from some business risks (Detthamrong et al., 2017). The performance and operating profit of the company are related to the number of board members, board independence, gender diversity and CEO duality (Bhagat & Bolton, 2019). Therefore, BD with characteristics such as size, independent members, female, and duality are used as moderator variables in this study.

Jensen and Meckling (1976) argued that the BD has a monitoring and management role, ensuring a clear separation between corporate control and the company's daily operations. A large BD with diverse expertise will promote sound strategic decision-making, minimise risks, closely monitor finances and reduce agency costs arising from managers' personal interests (Jensen & Meckling, 1976a). Large boards can enhance corporate legitimacy and reputation, attract investors, and increase operating efficiency, so some studies provide empirical evidence that large boards have a positive impact on operating profits (Akhter & Hassan, 2024; Lee & Ko, 2022; Shakri et al., 2024). Furthermore, a board with diverse members in terms of expertise and experience is even more beneficial in an emerging economy where capital market regulations are not yet fully established and companies rely heavily on debt (Pham & Nguyen, 2019). Furthermore, the monitoring role of the board of directors is enhanced by independent outside members (Detthamrong et al., 2017). Independent board members provide better monitoring, solve the agency problem (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), ensure the interests of shareholders and investors, and increase growth and

operating profits (Muniandy & Hillier, 2015). With the presence of independent members, managers in emerging market companies will be subject to strict supervision, so investment decisions from borrowed capital are more effective (Pham & Nguyen, 2019), ensuring transparency and efficiency in debt use and independent members increase operating profits (Muniandy & Hillier, 2015; Gharios et al., 2024). Meanwhile, duality concentrates power in the hands of the CEO, leading to a lack of independent supervision, creating information asymmetry, and reducing operating profits. At the same time, according to agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), gender diversity in the board of directors increases operating efficiency. Resource dependence theory suggests that board members, especially women, can enhance resources and improve efficiency. Women on the board of directors are considered important with the belief that they will bring new expertise, thereby having a positive impact on profits (Liu et al., 2014). Several studies acknowledge the positive impact of board gender diversity on operating profits (Amedi & Mustafa, 2020; Gharios et al., 2024). From the above arguments, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₂: Board size moderates the negative impact of CT on operating profits.

H₃: Board independence increases the positive impact of CT on operating profits.

H₄: CEO duality increases the negative impact of CT on profitability.

H₅: Female board members increase the positive impact on the relationship between CT and operating profit.

Methodology

Research sample and data.

The dataset used in this study comprises the financial reports and annual reports of listed companies on the Vietnamese stock market from 2015 to 2023. The total number of listed companies as of December 31, 2023 is 739 companies (412 listed companies on HOSE and 327 listed companies on HNX). After excluding companies in the finance, banking, insurance, and securities sectors, the final sample is 588 companies, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Distribution of companies in the research sample by sectors

Industry-wise sample distribution	Number of Observations			Frequency(%)
	HOSE	HNX	Total	
- Wholesale	24	23	47	8%
- Retail	11	7	18	3.1%
- Technology and Information	3	22	25	4.26%
- Professional, scientific and technological service	3	7	10	1.71%
- Support services	0	3	3	0.51%
- Accommodation and food service	3	3	6	1.02%
- Extractive	9	18	27	4.6%
- Arts, entertainment and recreation	1	0	1	0.17%
- Manufacture	110	90	200	34%
- Agricultural production	7	4	11	1.87%
- Utilities	28	14	42	7.15%
- Transportation and warehousing	29	27	56	9.53%
- Construction and Real estate	80	62	142	24.16%

Source: Author's own compilation

Measuring variables in the model

Dependent variable: This study uses return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) to measure the company's profitability, with profit calculated as earnings before tax (Pham & Nguyen, 2019)

Independent variable: In this study, we use total leverage at book value because, according to Jermias and Yigit (2019), managers tend to focus on book value leverage, arguing that debt is better supported by local assets than growth opportunities, making market CT unreliable (Frank & Goyal, 2009). Therefore, CT is measured as total liabilities divided by total assets (Ayaz et al., 2021).

Moderator variables: The moderator variables are BD, such as board size, board independence, board gender diversity, and CEO duality. Board size refers to the number of members on the board, board independence represents the percentage of independent non-executive members among the total number of board members, and board gender diversity represents the percentage of female members on the board. CEO duality takes the value of 1 if the chair of the board is also the CEO. Otherwise, it takes the value of 0.

Control variables: To overcome the suboptimal model, we controlled for several factors that may affect operating profit, including company size, audit quality, and company age. It is argued that large firms use more debt than small firms, which positively impacts profitability, measured as the logarithm of total assets (Jermias & Yigit, 2019). Audit quality is also a factor that increases operating profit. According to (Mahajan & Singh, 2013), company age is associated with experience, expertise, and the older the company, the larger the market share and the more customers, so profits tend to be higher.

Research model

To empirically test the proposed hypotheses, this study builds a regression model based on the underlying theories as well as related studies. Research model 1 is established to answer hypothesis 1. Research model 2 is used to answer hypotheses 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Model 1: $\text{Profit}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{CT}_{it} + \beta_2 * \text{Size}_{it} + \beta_3 * \text{Audit}_{it} + \beta_4 * \text{AGEFIRM}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$

Model 2: $\text{Profit}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{CT}_{it} + \beta_2 * \text{BDSIZE}_{it} + \beta_3 * \text{BDIN}_{it} + \beta_4 * \text{BDGEN}_{it} + \beta_5 * \text{DUAL}_{it} + \beta_6 * \text{Interactions}_{it} + \beta_7 * \text{Size}_{it} + \beta_8 * \text{Audit}_{it} + \beta_9 * \text{AGEFIRM}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$

Where:

Profit is the dependent variable measured by ROA and ROE

CT is the independent variable representing CT measured by book value.

β_0 : is the intercept coefficient; β_i are the regression coefficients.

Interaction variables are moderating variables to assess the moderating impact of board characteristics on the impact of CT on operating profits. The method of measuring moderating variables is based on research of (Pham & Nguyen, 2019) and, from the perspective of econometrics (Baron & Kenny, 1986). Specifically:

Interaction variable $\text{CT} * \text{BDSIZE} = (\text{CT} - \text{mean of CT}) * (\text{BDSIZE} - \text{Mean of BDSIZE})$

Interaction variable $\text{CT} * \text{BDIN} = (\text{CT} - \text{Mean of CT}) * (\text{BDIN} - \text{Mean of BDIN})$

Interaction variable $\text{CT} * \text{BDGEN} = (\text{CT} - \text{Mean of CT}) * (\text{BDGEN} - \text{Mean of BDGEN})$

Interaction variable $\text{CT} * \text{DUAL} = (\text{CT} - \text{Mean of CT}) * \text{DUAL}$

Research results and discussion

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents a descriptive statistic of the variables used in the study: dependent variables, independent variables and control variables. Two important indicators are shown related to operating profit and CT. The average values of ROA and ROE are 0.072 (7.2%) and 0.133 (13.3%) respectively. This result acknowledges that listed companies in Vietnam from 2015 to 2023 have relatively good operating performance, but the results are also similar in the study (Le & Phan, 2017) with ROA and ROE of 6.3% and 10.3%, respectively. Meanwhile, the CT of the companies in the research sample have an average debt ratio of 46.6%, 0.6% higher than 46% in the study of Dang et al., (2019), higher than 43% (Bui et al, 2023) but much lower than 51.9% (Le & Phan, 2019) and with a standard deviation of 22.8%.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
ROA	5.292	0.072	0.087	-0.471	0.817
ROE	5.292	0.133	0.141	-0.884	0.987
CT	5.292	0.466	0.223	0.0006	1.143
BDSIZE	5.292	5.417	1.217	3	12
BDIN	5.292	0.153	0.17	0	0.833
BDGEN	5.292	0.175	0.168	0	0.8
FSIZE	5.292	11.9533	0.7061	10.13	14.825
AGEFIRM	5.292	28.1565	15.414	1	134

Note: ROA: return on total assets; ROE is return on equity; CT is the liabilities on total assets; BDSIZE is a number of board members; BDIN is a number of board outsider members divided by a total number of boards. FSIZE is a firm’s size, measuring the natural logarithm of the total assets; AGEFIRM: the distance between the time of firm establishment and the study period.

Source: Research findings from Stata 18

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics for dummy variables

AUDIT	Freq	Percent	Cum	DUAL	Freq	Percent	Cum
0	3.931	74.28	74.28	0	4.560	86.17	86.17
1	1.361	25.72	100	1	732	13.83	100
Total	5.292	100		Total	5.292	100	

Note: Dual take 1 for chairman who also serves as the CEO otherwise 0; Audit take 1 if the company is audited by BIG4, otherwise 0.

Source: Research findings from Stata 18

Check for correlation and multicollinearity

The study continued to test the correlation between variables in the research model and check for multicollinearity. The results of the correlation test are shown in Table 4, with correlation coefficients all less than 0.2 and the VIF inflation factor also less than 2. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no multicollinearity phenomenon, and the variables are not strongly correlated.

Table 4: Pearson correlations and VIF value

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Roa (1)	1										
ROE (2)		1									
CT (3)	-0.35***	0.04***	1								
Bdin(4)	0.036***	0.02	-0.04***	1							
Bdsize (5)	0.09***	0.12***	0.04***	0.08***	1						
Bgen (6)	0.04***	0.01	-0.12***	0.07***	-0.03**	1					
Dual (7)	0.02	0.04***	-0.02	-0.03***	-0.018	0.04**	1				
Audit (8)	0.08***	0.12***	0.03**	0.12***	0.17***	-0.01	-0.04***	1			
Fsize (9)	-0.04**	0.09***	0.35***	0.18***	0.32***	-0.02	-0.06***	0.44***	1		
Agefirm (10)	0.06***	0.05***	0.06***	-0.06***	0.03**	-0.07***	-0.05***	0.001	0.03**	1	
CT*dual (11)	-0.08***	0.05***	0.35***	-0.01	0.04***	-0.04***	-0.07***	0.03**	0.15***	0.02*	1
CT*bdgen (12)	0.02	0.02*	-0.01	0.03**	-0.01	-0.11***	0.01	0.04***	0.02*	-0.08***	0.04***
CT*bdin (13)	-0.019	-0.02	-0.03**	-0.07***	0.01	0.03**	0.01	-0.001	-0.03**	-0.01	-0.05***
CT*bdsizes (14)	-0.04***	0.04***	-0.12***	0.01	0.01	-0.001	0.03**	-0.04***	-0.01	-0.07***	-0.04***
Mean VIF											

Regression results of model 1

The data used in the study is panel data for the period 2015 to 2023, so the author has performed F-test, LM-test and Hausman-test. The results related to the 3 tests respectively have P-values less than the 5% significance level (When the dependent variable is ROA: Prob>F = 0.000; Prob>Chiba2 = 0.000 and Prob>Chi2 = 0.000. When the dependent variable is ROE: Prob>F = 0.0024 and Prob>Chiba2 = 1.000). This means that the most suitable regression model is FEM for both dependent variables, ROA and ROE, which represent operating profit.

Next, the study conducted a heteroscedasticity test and an autocorrelation test, with the results being Prob> Chi2 = 0.012 and Prob> chi2 = 0.000, respectively, meaning that the model suffered from heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. Therefore, the study used the FGLS model to overcome the above shortcomings (Table 5)

Table 5. Regression results with dependent variables ROA and ROE

	FGLS (Model 1)		FGLS (model 2)	
	ROA	ROE	ROA	ROE
CT	-0.160*** (-29.08)	-0.297*** (-5.14)	-0.154*** (-27.62)	-0.06*** (-5.74)
BDSIZE			0.00646*** -6.73	0.01*** (6.18)
BDGEN			0.00468 (0.78)	0.01 (1.05)
BDIN			0.001 (0.13)	-0.01 (-0.69)
DUAL			0.01* (2.42)	0.023*** (4.3)
CT * BDSIZE			-0.03*** (-6.21)	-0.023*** (-3.15)
CT*BDIN			-0.03 (-1.02)	-0.06 (-1.16)
CT*BDGEN			0.05* (1.7)	0.07 (1.48)
CT*DUAL			0.043** (2.86)	0.11*** (4.31)
FSIZE	0.011*** (5.55)	0.035* (1.68)	0.005*** (2.36)	0.01*** (3.84)
AGEFIRM	0.0004*** (5.7)	-0.0001 (-0.18)	0.0004*** (6.19)	0.0005*** (3.84)
AUDIT	0.009** (3.01)	0.0253 (0.81)	0.013*** (4.58)	0.03*** (5.27)
CONST	0.0002 (0.01)	-0.169 (-0.72)	-0.036* (1.67)	-0.04 (-1.16)
N	5.292	5.292	5.292	5.292

Note: *t* statistics in parentheses; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: Research findings from Stata 18

The regression results in Table 5 confirm that CT has a negative and significant impact at 1% for both dependent variable models, ROA and ROE. Meanwhile, the control variables FSIZE, AGEFIRM, and AUDIT have a positive and significant impact at a 99% confidence level when measuring profit by ROA and ROE. This result is consistent with the view that in developing markets, CT increases costs due to interest payments, thus limiting capital for operations, and this affects operating profits (Dang et al., 2019; Dawar, 2014; Nguyen et al., 2023; Le & Phan, 2019).

Regression results of model 2

For the model with the moderator variable of the BD, the author also conducted related tests and the FGLS model was also used to evaluate the results because the model was subject to heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation. The regression results in Table 5 show a negative and significant impact of the moderator variable CT*BDSIZE (1% significance level for both ROA and ROE) on the relationship between capital structure and profitability. This means that hypothesis 02 is accepted, which is that the larger the board of directors, the greater the negative impact of capital structure on profitability.

With coefficients $\beta = -0.03$ and $\beta = -0.06$ at P value = 0.331, P value = 0.271 for ROA, ROE, respectively, it means that the moderating variable BDIN has a negative impact but is not statistically significant. This result rejects hypothesis H3. The research results reflect the true role of independent members in the BD in the Vietnam stock market. That is, the independent member has not performed the monitoring function properly, so the role of the independent member is not clearly demonstrated, and the independent member does not affect the profit (Quoc Trung, 2022). Meanwhile, DUAL has a positive impact on the relationship between CT and ROA, ROE at the 1% significance level. This means that this result is consistent with the view of agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) when it is assumed that holding two positions reduces agency costs, increases performance, so hypothesis H4 is accepted for both ROA and ROE. But for BDGEN regulation, it only has a positive and significant impact on ROA, while ROE is not significant.

Thus, the empirical results acknowledge that in the absence of the moderating role of the BD characteristics, CT has a negative and significant impact on operating profit. But when using the moderating role of the BD, BDSIZE reduces the negative impact of CT on profits, BDIN does not have any effect on the relationship between CT and profit, duality completely changes the initial impact of CT on profit, meaning that with the management of a concurrent CEO, the use of a large debt level increases operating profit and finally the moderating impact increases the positive impact of CT on profit through the ROA and ROE.

In addition, the study also acknowledges that control variables such as company size, age of firm and audit quality all increase operating profit in both cases where the dependent variables are ROA and ROE. This means that in the case of considering CT, with or without BD regulation, the variables FSIZE, AUDIT, and AGEFIRM all have positive and significant impacts on operating profit.

Conclusion

The research results acknowledge that CT tends to decrease the profitability of listed companies in Vietnam. In emerging economies, financing through debt is costly, with high interest payments and reduced profits; however, the use of debt is inevitable in emerging markets. The study also acknowledges that CG characteristics, such as female directors on boards and CEO duality, increase the efficiency of debt use and enhance profits. Furthermore, BDSIZE mitigates the negative impact of CT on profits, suggesting that managers of listed companies in Vietnam should consider this issue when making decisions on CT. Nevertheless, the independent role of the BD remains unclear when examining CT and its impact on profits in the context of listed companies in Vietnam during this period.

Our study contributes to the existing literature in several aspects: (1) Providing evidence that CG features play a useful role in improving the efficiency of CT; (2) Consistent results on the negative impact of CT on operating profits in the emerging market of Vietnam. Therefore, through the research results, we recommend some relevant policy implications: (1) Listed companies in emerging economies when using debt instruments to finance their business activities should build effective CG mechanisms to promote operating efficiency such as using more members on the BD, adding female members to the BD as well as the role of CEO duality; (2) For policy-making agencies, there should be reforms in the capital market, build a legal framework for the capital market, strengthen coordination and information sharing among agencies in management and supervision, and issue policies related to improving risks and increasing capacity at commercial banks. These policies are the basis for lowering lending interest rates and reducing pressure on capital costs for listed companies.

Although the study has achieved its objectives and contributed some important aspects to the underlying theory, the study still has some limitations. These are: (1) the study has not considered the possible endogeneity problem; (2) the study only considers CT from the perspective of total debt, so it cannot have an accurate assessment of how debt types affect operating profits; (3) the research data sample is only conducted in the Vietnamese market, so the conclusions are not highly generalizable. These limitations can be an additional research direction in the future.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank all lecturers and the Rector of the University of Finance - Marketing, HCMC, Vietnam. Besides, this research is supported by the University of Finance – Marketing

References

- Akhter, W., & Hassan, A. (2024). Does corporate social responsibility mediate the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance? Empirical evidence from <scp>BRICS</scp> countries. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 31(1), 566–578. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2586>
- Amedi, A. M. R., & Mustafa, A. S. (2020). Board characteristics and firm performance: Evidence from manufacture sector of Jordan. *Accounting Analysis Journal*, 9(3), 146–151.
- Ayaz, M., Mohamed Zabri, S., & Ahmad, K. (2021). An empirical investigation on the impact of capital structure on firm performance: evidence from Malaysia. *Managerial Finance*, 47(8), 1107–1127. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-11-2019-0586>

- Ayuba, H., Bambale, A. J., Ibrahim, M., & Sulaiman, S. (2019). Effects of Financial Performance, capital structure and Firm Size on Firms' Value of Insurance Companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(1), 57–74.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173>
- Bhagat, S., & Bolton, B. (2019). Corporate governance and firm performance: The sequel. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 58, 142–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2019.04.006>
- Bui, T. N., Nguyen, X. H., & Pham, K. T. (2023). The Effect of capital structure on Firm Value: A Study of Companies Listed on the Vietnamese Stock Market. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(3), 100. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs11030100>
- Chowdhury, A., & Chowdhury, S. P. (2010). Impact of capital structure on firm's value: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Peer - Reviewed and Open Access Journal*, 3(3), 111–122.
- Dakua, S. (2019). Effect of determinants on financial leverage in Indian steel industry: A study on capital structure. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 24(1), 427–436. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.1671>
- Dang, H. N., Vu, V. T. T., Ngo, X. T., & Hoang, H. T. V. (2019). Study the Impact of Growth, Firm Size, Capital Structure, and Profitability on Enterprise Value: Evidence of Enterprises in Vietnam. *Journal of Corporate Accounting & Finance*, 30(1), 144–160. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcaf.22371>
- Dawar, V. (2014). Agency theory, capital structure and firm performance: some Indian evidence. *Managerial Finance*, 40(12), 1190–1206. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MF-10-2013-0275>
- Detthamrong, U., Chancharat, N., & Vithessonthi, C. (2017). Corporate governance, Capital structure and firm performance: Evidence from Thailand. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 42, 689–709. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2017.07.011>
- Dharwadkar, B., George, G., & Brandes, P. (2000). Privatization in Emerging Economies: An Agency Theory Perspective. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(3), 650–669. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2000.3363533>
- Frank, M. Z., & Goyal, V. K. (2009). Capital structure Decisions: Which Factors Are Reliably Important? *Financial Management*, 38(1), 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-053X.2009.01026.x>
- Gharios, R., Awad, A. B., Abu Khalaf, B., & Seissian, L. A. (2024). The Impact of Board Gender Diversity on European Firms' Performance: The Moderating Role of Liquidity. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 17(8), 359. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm17080359>
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency costs and Ownership Structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 4(4), 305–360.
- Jermias, J. (2008). The relative influence of competitive intensity and business strategy on the relationship between financial leverage and performance. *The British Accounting Review*, 40(1), 71–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2007.11.001>
- Jermias, J., & Yigit, F. (2019). Factors affecting leverage during a financial crisis: Evidence from Turkey. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 19(2), 171–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2018.07.002>
- Khan, A., Qureshi, M. A., & Davidsen, P. I. (2021). A system dynamics model of capital structure policy for firm value maximization. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 38(4), 503–516. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2693>
- Kijkasiwat, P., Hussain, A., & Mumtaz, A. (2022). Corporate Governance, Firm Performance and Financial Leverage across Developed and Emerging Economies. *Risks*, 10(10), 185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/risks10100185>
- Kraus, A., & Litzenberger, R. H. (1973). A State-Preference Model of Optimal Financial Leverage. *The Journal of Finance*, 28(4), 911. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2978343>
- Kumar, N., & Singh, J. P. (2013). Effect of board size and promoter ownership on firm value: some empirical findings from India. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 13(1), 88–98. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14720701311302431>

- Le, T. P. V., & Phan, T. B. N. (2017). CT and firm performance: Empirical evidence from a small transition country. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 42, 710–726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2017.07.012>
- Lee, S.-Y., & Ko, E.-J. (2022). Effects of founder CEO duality and board size on foreign IPOs' survival in US markets. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 22(5), 1054–1077. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-04-2021-015z>
- Liu, Y., Wei, Z., & Xie, F. (2014). Do women directors improve firm performance in China? *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 28, 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2013.11.016>
- Mahajan, P., & Singh, F. (2013). How do Pre-slowdown Financial Characteristics Impact the Firms' Relative Financial Performance during Economic Recession? An Empirical Investigation. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 9(4), 369–378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2319510X14523105>
- Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. H. (1958). The Cost of Capital, Corporate Finance and the Theory of Investment. *The American Economic Review*, 48(3), 261–297.
- Muniandy, B., & Hillier, J. (2015). Board independence, investment opportunity set and performance of South African firms. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 35, 108–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2014.11.003>
- Myers, S. C., & Majluf, N. S. (1984). Corporate financing and investment decisions when firms have information that investors do not have. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 13(2), 187–221. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(84\)90023-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(84)90023-0)
- Nguyen, S. L., Pham, C. D., Truong, T. V., Phi, T. V., Le, L. T., & Vu, T. T. T. (2023). Relationship between capital structure and Firm Profitability: Evidence from Vietnamese Listed Companies. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs11010045>
- Pham, H. S. T., & Nguyen, D. T. (2019). The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial leverage–profitability relation. *Management Research Review*, 43(4), 387–409. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-03-2019-0136>
- Quoc Trung, N. K. (2022). Board of directors characteristics affect commercial banks' performance – evidence in Vietnam. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2060164>
- Sarkar, J., & Sarkar, S. (2008). Debt and corporate governance in emerging economies: Evidence from India¹. *Economics of Transition*, 16(2), 293–334. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0351.2008.00307.x>
- Shakri, I. H., Yong, J., & Xiang, E. (2024). Corporate governance and firm performance: Evidence from political instability, political ideology, and corporate governance reforms in Pakistan. *Economics & Politics*, 36(3), 1633–1663. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecpo.12303>
- Truong, T. N., & Nguyen, V. C. (2024). The impact of the board of directors and the audit committee on the transparency of financial information of companies listed in a frontier market. *Heliyon*, 10(22), e40188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e40188>
- World Bank (2018). *The World Bank Annual Report 2018 (Vol. 1 of 3) (English)*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/630671538158537244>